

IMPROVING PATIENTS' SELF-EFFICACY AND KNOWLEDGE OF MEDICATIONS

Joelle Otteson, DNP, RN; Ahlam Jadalla, PhD, RN; Joy Goebel, PhD, RN, FPCN

Background

- Adverse drug events (ADEs) result in over 700,000 Emergency Department (ED) visits annually
- Older adults (≥ 65 years) are:
 - 2XS as likely to experience ADEs
 - 7XS more likely to require hospitalization
 - take ≥ 5 medications on average
- Adverse drug events (ADEs) result in over 700,000 Emergency Department (ED) visits annually

Purpose Statement

- To improve knowledge and self-efficacy of medication management among adults aged ≥65 years in a primary care setting

Methods

- Quality Improvement project
- Self-Efficacy in managing medications assessed with the Self-Efficacy for Appropriate Medication Use Scale (SEAMS)
- Knowledge assessed with the Medication Knowledge Assessment Tool (MKAT)
- Standardized face-to-face education, follow up phone calls
- MKAT and SEAMS tools administered at baseline, one-, and two-month intervals

Plan-Do-Study-Act Framework

Results

Lessons Learned

- Patients rely on their medication lists—RN must ensure accuracy
- Patients were least likely to know the correct dosage of their medication
- Initial teaching may be time consuming
- A longer project time line may provide more evidence of efficacy

Recommendations

- Assess patient knowledge of their medication regimen at each visit
- Stress importance of knowing medication name, dose, schedule, and purpose
- Take the time to reconcile medication lists at each visit
- Encourage all patients to carry an accurate medication list to all medical visits
- Accept steady change as success

Conclusion

Older adults in primary care settings respond positively to the “back to basics” approach based on face-to-face, standardized teaching.

Links to Tools/References

Assessment Tools

Reference List